

DEGRADATION OF CARBON FIBERS BY MOLTEN ALUMINUM

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Summary

The degradation of carbon fibers by molten aluminum was investigated by measuring the change in strength of the fibers. Two types of carbon fibers; polyacrylonitrile(PAN)-based and pitch-based carbon fiber, were used in the present study. Tows of carbon fibers were impregnated with the slurry of aluminum powder. The impregnated tows were hot pressed in vacuum at temperatures in the liquid phase of aluminum. The matrix of the hot pressed composites was dissolved with sodium hydroxide solution and the fibers were extracted from the fabricated composites. Then, the extracted fibers were tension tested with a testing machine for mono-filament and observed with a scanning electron microscope(SEM).

The tensile strength of the carbon fibers rapidly decreased after the contact with molten aluminum and gradually decreased with time afterwards while kept in contact with molten aluminum. The general tendency of the degradation in strength was similar for both carbon fibers. However, the rate of degradation of the pitch-based carbon fiber was less than that of the PAN-based carbon fiber. The SEM micrographs showed that aluminum carbide crystals were formed at the surface of the fiber, not as a continuous layer on a surface, but as platelets nearly perpendicular to the fiber axis. Less aluminum carbide crystals were found on the surface of pitch-based carbon fiber than on the PAN-based carbon fiber. The SEM photographs of the fractured surface of the fibers showed that the fracture had initiated at the root portion of aluminum carbide crystals. The root portion of the aluminum carbide crystal acts as a notch on the fiber surface, so that the strength of the fiber is weakened.

Introduction

Fiber reinforced metal matrix composites have the high potential as materials for the aerospace uses because of their expected high specific properties. In the case of carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composites, however, the interfacial reaction between fiber and matrix is apt to occur during composite fabrication in the liquid phase of aluminum and it causes the degradation of the fibers.

The present investigation was carried out to reveal the degradation behaviour of carbon fibers by molten aluminum and to determine the morphology of the reaction products between fiber and matrix.

Experimental

Two types of carbon fibers; polyacrylonitrile(PAN)-based carbon fiber (Toray T-300) and pitch-based carbon fiber (Kureha T-101S) were used in this study. Tows of carbon fibers were impregnated with the slurry of aluminum powder (-250 mesh). After drying the impregnated tows, the tows were cut into pieces of a fixed length and hot pressed with a graphite die in vacuum at temperatures in the liquid phase of aluminum. The conditions for the hot pressing are as follows: pressure; 1 kg/cm^2 , temperature; $953 \text{ K}(680^\circ\text{C})$ - $1073 \text{ K}(800^\circ\text{C})$, holding time; 30s-10min.

The matrix of the hot pressed composites was dissolved with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The carbon fibers extracted from the composites were tension tested with a testing machine for mono-filament. The extracted carbon fibers were observed with a scanning electron microscope(SEM) and a transmission electron microscope(TEM). The differential thermal analysis-(DTA) was made to distinguish the difference between the PAN-based and the pitch-based fibers.

Results

Fig. 1 shows the change in tensile strength of the PAN-based carbon fiber with time after the contact with molten aluminum. Fig. 2 shows the change in tensile strength with temperature. The tensile strength of the carbon fiber decreases rapidly at first and dose not change so much afterwards while kept in contact with molten aluminum, and it decreases

Fig. 1 Change in tensile strength of PAN-based carbon fiber with time.

Fig. 2 Change in tensile strength of PAN-based carbon fiber with temperature.

Fig. 3 Change in diameter of PAN-based carbon fiber with time.

with increasing temperature. Fig. 3 shows the change in diameter of the PAN-based carbon fiber corresponding to Fig. 1. Though the tensile strength of the fiber decreases, the diameter of the fiber is almost unchanged. Fig. 4 shows the change in tensile strength of the pitch-based carbon fiber with time and Fig. 5 shows the change in tensile strength with temperature. The degradation behaviours of both fibers are compared in Fig. 6 which is represented by the relative strength. The general tendency of the degradation in strength is similar for both fibers, however, the rate of degradation of the pitch-based carbon fiber is much less than that of the PAN-based carbon fiber. Fig. 7 shows the results of differential thermal analysis for both fibers. In the case of pitch-based carbon fiber, the peak showing the chemical reaction between fiber and matrix shifts to the higher temperature side.

The SEM micrographs exhibiting the reaction products at the surface of the fiber are shown in Figs. 8 and 9. More and larger reaction products are found on the surface of the PAN-based carbon fiber than on the pitch-based carbon fiber for the nearly same contact conditions. Furthermore, the number and size of the reaction product increase with increasing temperature. These SEM micrographs are consistent with the above mentioned experimental results (Figs. 6 and 7). Fig. 10 shows the well-developed reaction products on the surface of the PAN-based carbon fiber. It is shown that the large reaction products are composed of a few

Fig. 4 Change in tensile strength of pitch-based carbon fiber with time.

Fig. 5 Change in tensile strength of pitch-based carbon fiber with temperature.

Fig. 6 Comparison of degradation in strength of PAN-based fiber and pitch-based fiber.

Fig. 7 Differential thermal analysis of degradation process.

coarse grains and the reaction products grow into aluminum matrix with platelet shape nearly perpendicular to the fiber axis.

A selected area electron diffraction (SAD) analysis was made to determine the crystal structure of the reaction product at the surface of the fiber. Fig. 11 shows the TEM micrographs of the reaction products and the corresponding SAD patterns. From the SAD patterns, the reaction product was determined to be aluminum carbide (Al_4C_3). A smaller reaction product shows a spotty ring pattern of polycrystalline structure (Fig. 11 (a)), but a larger reaction product shows fewer spots corresponding to coarse grains or, in some cases, a single crystal (Fig. 11 (b)). Fig. 12 is the micrographs of the fracture surface of the PAN-based carbon fiber. It is exhibited that the fracture initiated at the root portion of the aluminum carbide crystal. Thus the formation of aluminum carbide at the fiber surface causes the degradation in strength of the fiber.

In order to prevent the degradation of carbon fiber, the effect of the addition of silicon to aluminum matrix was investigated with using Al-10.5% Si alloy as the matrix material. As shown in Fig. 1, however, the degradation behaviour of the carbon fiber in Al-10.5% Si alloy matrix was almost the same as the case without silicon.

Discussion

It is known that wetting between carbon fiber and molten aluminum is not good. In the present study, the liquid phase hot pressing of the carbon fiber tows impregnated with aluminum powder was adopted to ensure the contact between carbon fiber and molten aluminum from the beginning of each experimental run.

From the SAD analysis, the reaction product between the carbon fibers and molten aluminum was determined to be aluminum carbide Al_4C_3 . It was observed from the SEM micrographs and SAD patterns that minute particles of aluminum carbide were formed at the surface of carbon fiber at the early stage of the contact with molten aluminum, and smaller aluminum carbide crystals had a polycrystalline structure and larger crystals were composed of coarse grains or, in some cases, they were single crystal. A hypothetical process of the formation of aluminum carbide crystal at the interface between the carbon fiber and molten aluminum is schematically

953K(680°C), 1min

1073K(800°C), 5min

Fig. 8 SEM micrographs of PAN-based carbon fibers.

953K(680°C), 3min

1073K(800°C), 3min

Fig. 9 SEM micrographs of pitch-based carbon fibers.

1073K(800°C), 5min

Fig. 10 SEM micrograph of well-developed reaction products.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11 TEM micrographs and SAD patterns of reaction product at the surface of PAN-based carbon fiber.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 12 SEM micrographs of fracture surface of PAN-based carbon fiber.

Fig. 13 Schematic illustration of hypothetical process of Al_4C_3 crystal formation at the interface between carbon fiber and molten aluminum.

illustrated in Fig. 13, that is, 1) formation of minute aluminum carbide crystals at the surface of carbon fiber, 2) cohesion of the minute crystals, 3) grain growth of the carbide crystal into aluminum, 4) simultaneous aluminum carbide formation inside the carbon fiber, and 5) growth to a single crystal. The crystal structure of Al_4C_3 has been reported to be a hexagonal structure (1). A carbide crystal in Fig. 8 has a six sided polygonal shape which corresponds to a single crystal with a hexagonal structure.

It is shown from the micrograph of the fracture surface of the fiber (Fig. 12 (a)) that the fracture of the fiber initiated at the notch like flaw at the surface of the fiber. Another micrograph (Fig. 12 (b)) exhibits that aluminum carbide grows into the inside of carbon fiber just like a root of carbide crystal. Because of the brittleness of aluminum carbide, the root portion of carbide crystal acts as a notch on a fiber surface when the fiber is pulled. So, the strength of the carbon fiber is weakened by the formation of aluminum carbide at the surface of the fiber. Shorshorov et al. (2) reported that aluminum carbide crystals formed at the interface between carbon fiber and matrix grow into the matrix at first and then grew into the inside of the fiber at the later stage of reaction. It is consistent with the root formation of aluminum carbide crystals in the above mentioned process. The rapid decrease at the early stage and the gradual change in fiber strength afterwards while kept in contact with molten aluminum can be explained by the notch effect of the carbide crystal at the surface of the fiber, assuming that the notch has about the same size. And the decrease in fiber strength with increasing temperature is also explained as the growth of the root portion at higher temperatures. As aluminum carbide is formed as platelets at the fiber surface nearly perpendicular to the fiber axis, the measured apparent diameter of the fiber extracted from the matrix remains unchanged compared with the remarkable change in fiber strength.

Amateau (3) reported that the degradation in strength of the pitch-based carbon fiber was less than that of the PAN-based carbon fiber. Kitamura (4) indicated that the high modulus type fibers of the PAN-based carbon fiber were less degraded by molten aluminum than the high strength type fibers, and furthermore, even the high modulus carbon fibers were easily degraded after oxidation of the fiber surface. This difference in degradation behaviour by the fiber type may be attributed to the difference in the crystal structure of the fiber surface.

In the present experiment, the addition of silicon to the aluminum matrix showed no obvious effect on the improvement of the degradation of

the carbon fiber. However, the liquidus temperature of the aluminum matrix can be lowered by the silicon alloying. If a lower fabrication temperature is adopted, the degradation of the carbon fibers will be reduced.

Conclusions

The degradation behaviour of the PAN-based carbon fiber and the pitch-based carbon fiber by molten aluminum was investigated. The pitch-based carbon fiber is less degraded by molten aluminum than the PAN-based carbon fiber. The aluminum carbide crystals are formed at the fiber surface with a platelet shape nearly perpendicular to the fiber axis at the early stage of the contact with molten aluminum and grow inside the carbon fiber afterwards. The root portion of the carbide crystal acts as a notch on the fiber surface when the fiber is pulled, so that the fiber is weakened.

References

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